

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: In recent years, the importance of advanced technologies and innovation in the development of the economy is increasing. The latest technologies can improve the efficiency of production and business processes. Traditional approaches and ways of working are changing as the latest technologies penetrate into all new areas and fields of human activity.

Keywords: environment, ICT, 50 per cent, trade and public services, artificial intelligence, Virtual learning environments and distance learning in education, media algorithms

Annotatsiya: So'nggi yillarda iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda ilg'or texnologiyalar va innovatsiyalarning ahamiyati oshib bormoqda. Eng yangi texnologiyalar ishlab chiqarish va biznes jarayonlarining samaradorligini oshirishi mumkin. Eng yangi texnologiyalar inson faoliyatining barcha yangi sohalariga va sohalariga kirib borishi bilan an'anaviy yondashuvlar va ish uslublari o'zgaradi.

Kalit so'zlar: atrof-muhit, AKT, 50 foiz, savdo va davlat xizmatlari, sun'iy intellekt, Virtual ta'lim muhitlari va ta'limda masofaviy ta'lim, media algoritmlari

Аннотация: В последние годы возрастает значение передовых технологий и инноваций в развитии экономики. Новейшие технологии позволяют повысить эффективность производственных и бизнес-процессов. По мере проникновения новейших технологий во все новые сферы и области человеческой деятельности меняются традиционные подходы и способы работы.

Ключевые слова: окружающая среда, ИКТ, 50 процентов, торговля и государственные услуги, искусственный интеллект, виртуальные среды обучения и дистанционное обучение в образовании, медиаалгоритмы

Benefits Of Technology to the Society: Technology has aided civilization in a variety of ways, the most notable of which are health care, education, and communication. It has also changed the way people enjoy themselves, participate in politics, and work. Society and technology are inextricably linked. On the other side, technology has made us anxious. Its misuse has poisoned the

environment and presented a significant threat to our lives and civilization. This needs the effective application of technology. On the impact of technological advances and contemporary comforts on the quality of life in modern society, there are two points of view. While some say that technological advancements have improved people's lives, others contend that they have had a negative impact.

Thus, it can lead to improved transactions by downloading and managing a certain level of network technologies from a set of technologies. to exchange information between buyers. For example: Platforms are secured, communication between taxi workers and reporting passengers. In addition, several platforms, the relationship between car owners and those who want to rent a car are otherwise evident.

Digital economy is a new direction in the world economy. Economically developed countries have made significant progress in this direction, while others are advancing in this direction. Therefore, almost all countries that have begun to transform their economies into a digital economy are facing the same problem - the lack of educational and scientific literature necessary for the training of qualified personnel in national languages in the 818 digital economy. The authors of this textbook, based on foreign sources of information on the digital economy and theoretical educational and scientific materials, tried to fill this gap a little. In conclusion, it can be said that the Digital economy cannot be imagined without modern information and communication technologies (ICT) and the Global Internet. The concepts of "digital economy", ICT and the Internet are inextricably linked.

In this way, social media algorithms can fuel the fragmentation of societies around the world. And yet they also have the potential to do the opposite. While technological advancements have both benefits and drawbacks, I contend that the benefits exceed the drawbacks, and so technological growth is good for modern civilization.

The impact of innovation and technology expansion on economic development has long been recognised. ICT increases the availability of information, forms new communication methods, reformats productive processes and improves the efficiency of many different economic activities. Digital technologies have advanced more rapidly than any innovation in our history – reaching around 50 per cent of the developing world's population in only two decades and transforming societies. By enhancing connectivity, financial inclusion, access to trade and public services, technology can be a great

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equaliser. In the health sector, for instance, AI-enabled frontier technologies are helping to save lives, diagnose diseases and extend life expectancy. In education, virtual learning environments and distance learning have opened up programmes to students who would otherwise be excluded. Public services are also becoming more accessible and accountable through blockchain-powered systems, and less bureaucratically burdensome as a result of AI assistance. Big data can also support more responsive and accurate policies and programmes. The ever-increasing realm of information technology has helped to improve many fields of public and private human life; like economy, business, information accessibility, governmental organizations, education, social ways and means of communication and entertainment etc.

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